

Prevalence, Forms, and Causes of Workplace Violence (WPV) in Enugu State University Teaching Hospital Parklane, Enugu

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ABSTRACT:

Background:

Due to the nature of their jobs, healthcare workers face a variety of workplace hazards, including violence from patients, their relatives, and colleagues

Aim/Objective

The study aimed to determine the prevalence of workplace violence (WPV), its forms, and causes/contributing factors among hospital workers at Enugu State University Teaching Hospital (ESUTH) Parklane

Methods

A cross-sectional descriptive study conducted in 2023 among healthcare workers (HCW) at Enugu State University Teaching Hospital using a pre-tested semi-structured self-administered questionnaire on “workplace violence in the health sector”, adapted from the International Labour Organization, International Council of Nurses, World Health Organization, and Public Services International (ILO/WHO/PSI). Proportionate allocation was used to select 388 respondents. Data were analyzed with SPSS version 26 and P value set at <0.05.

Results:

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How to Cite

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Among the participants, 37.6% had been victims of all forms of WPV at one point or the other. Verbal abuse was the most common form of WPV at 38.7%, followed at a short distance by bullying at 21.9%, physical attack was 16%, while sexual abuse stood at 8.8%. The majority (42%) of workplace violence was from patients, 30.6% by patients' relatives, and 27.4% by hospital staff. Female perpetrators were more (62.9%) than males (37.1%). Long patient wait time was reported as a cause by 50.3% of the respondents, unprofessional attitudes from healthcare professionals were reported by 37.9%, while relatives feeling that patients were in pain and not improving by 34.5%, and lack of security by 22.75%.

Conclusion:

This study showed that the prevalence of workplace violence among healthcare workers in Enugu State University Teaching Hospital is high. Therefore, there is need for measures to be put in place to curb this.

Keywords: Enugu, Workplace violence, Healthcare workers, Prevalence.

INTRODUCTION:

Workplace violence (WPV) is a significant occupational health issue, particularly affecting healthcare workers (HCWs).¹ Healthcare-related incidents account for 25% of the global burden of workplace violence.² Workplace violence is defined as the intentional use of physical or psychological force against individuals, aiming to harm, threaten, or insult them within the workplace.³ According to a report from the World Health Organization (WHO), between 8% and 38% of healthcare workers experience physical violence during their careers.⁴

A study conducted in Nigeria found that the majority of healthcare workers (88.1%) have experienced workplace violence.³ This violence can manifest in various forms, including verbal, physical, psychological, or sexual harassment. It can be either actual or threatened and may occur through small, repeated incidents that cumulatively result in significant harm. Individuals affected by workplace violence may experience a decline in their health and morale, leading to reduced productivity, economic waste, and increased absenteeism.^{1,5} The impact of such violence can also extend to the victim's family, co-workers,

patients, and employers, creating a ripple effect that affects society as a whole.

Workplace violence among healthcare workers is often perpetrated by patients, caregivers, or even co-workers. The causes of violence can stem from work conditions, personality or behavioural issues among patients and caregivers, as well as physical pain and financial stress experienced by patients. Despite the wide recognition of the existence of violence in the workplace, many cases remain unreported or underreported.⁷ This lack of reporting may be due to a culture of silence, other cultural practices, and fear of stigmatisation, which often enables the perpetrators to go without any consequence.

This study aims to determine the prevalence, forms, and causes of workplace violence against health workers at Enugu State University Teaching Hospital, Parklane Enugu. The findings from this study could be valuable in understanding the extent, forms, and causes of workplace violence among healthcare workers, as well as in developing effective strategies and policies to reduce it.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Study design

This study is a questionnaire-based, cross-sectional descriptive study conducted from July to September 2023.

Study Area

It took place at Enugu State University Teaching Hospital (ESUTH), Parklane, Enugu, and Southeast Nigeria. ESUTH is a prominent state teaching hospital situated in the heart of Enugu metropolis, serving the healthcare needs of the entire state as well as neighbouring states. Enugu State is one of the 36 states in Nigeria, located in the south-eastern region of the country. It is bordered to the north by Kogi and Benue States, to the east by Ebony State, to the west by Anambra State, and to the south by Abia State. The state comprises seventeen Local Government Areas (L.G.A.) and has an estimated total population of approximately 4,411,119, consisting of 2,249,670 males and 2,161,448 females.⁸

Study population

Participants in the study were hospital employees who had been working there for at least one year. This group included various clinical staff directly involved in patient care, such as medical doctors, pharmacists, nurses, laboratory scientists, radiographers, and physiotherapists. Additionally, non-clinical staff members, including Medical Record Officers, accounting officers/cashiers, ward attendants/orderlies, porters, cleaners, and security personnel, were also included in the study. Temporary staff members, as well as patients and their relatives, were part of the participant pool as well. Health workers, who have not been employed by the hospital for at least one year, as well as staff members on any form of leave at the time of the study, were excluded.

Sample size

The required sample size (n) is calculated using the formula $n = z^2pq / d^2$.⁹ The prevalence rate (p) of 64.4 percent was derived from a study conducted at

a Nigerian tertiary hospital.² To correct for non-response, 10% added as non-response rate $N = n + 10\%$ of $n = 352.3 + 10/100 \times 352.3 = 352.3 + 35.2 = 387.5 = 388$. The minimum sample size is 388 healthcare workers and patients/patient relatives in ESUTH Parklane, Enugu.

Sampling Technique

Using a list of all the health workers and patients/patient relatives from various departments/Specialty, the total number of respondents per department was selected by proportionate allocation. The respondents who met the inclusion criteria were selected by simple random sampling using the balloting method.

Instrument

A pre-tested semi-structured self-administered questionnaire on “workplace violence in the health sector”, adapted from the International Labour Organization, International Council of Nurses, World Health Organization, and Public Services International (ILO/WHO/PSI)⁶ was used.

Ethical considerations

Approval for the study was obtained from the ESUTH Health Research and Ethics committee before commencement of the study. All the participants were briefed on the study objectives, assured of the anonymity of the questionnaire, confidentiality/ voluntary nature of participation in the study, and also signed a written informed consent. Data was manually sorted out, input into the computer system and then imported into the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26.0 from Chicago IBM Co., Armonk, NY); cleaned, coded and analyzed. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$ and results presented in form of frequency tables.

RESULT:

This section reports the results from 388 respondents who completed the WHO questionnaire. In Table 1, 22.4% of the respondents were between the ages of 35 and 39, 17.0% were

aged 30 to 34 and 2.1% were 19 years old or younger. Additionally, Table 1 indicates that 69.1% of the respondents were male, while 30.9% were female. In terms of marital status, 55.2% were married, 27.1% were single, and 14.9% were separated or divorced. The majority of respondents (93.6%) identified as Christian, with a smaller

percentage (6.4%) identifying as Muslim. Regarding their occupational status, Table 1 shows that 17.0% of healthcare workers were nurses, 11.6% were physicians, 8.5% were physiotherapists, and only 0.8% worked in maintenance.

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics

Variables	Frequency (n=388)	Percentage (%)
Age (Years)		
19 and below	8	2.1
20-24	29	7.5
25-29	51	13.1
30-34	66	17.0
35-39	87	22.4
40-44	55	14.2
45-49	36	9.3
50-54	19	4.9
55-59	17	4.4
60 plus	20	5.2
Gender		
Female	120	30.9
Male	268	69.1
Marital Status		
Single	105	27.1
Married	214	55.2
Separated/divorced	58	14.9
Widowed	9	2.3
Others	2	0.5
Religion		
Christianity	363	93.6
Muslim	25	6.4
Occupational status		
Physician	45	11.6
Nurse	66	17.0
Pharmacist	31	8.0
Physiotherapist	33	8.5
Radiographer	16	4.1
Laboratory Scientist	7	1.8
Administrator/ Clerical	18	4.6
Security	4	1.0
Maintenance	3	0.8
Accounts	13	3.4

Figure 1 reveals that 38.7% experienced verbal abuse, 16% suffered a physical attack, 21.9% were bullied or mobbed, and 8.8% encountered sexual

harassment. Additionally, 37.6% reported being victims of all forms of workplace violence.

Figure 1: Percentage distribution of the prevalence of the Work-place based violence among hospital workers in ESUTH

In table 2, the majority of the respondents (84.0%) reported no physical attacks in the last 12 months, while 5.4% experienced 2 to 4 attacks, and 3.6% were assaulted several times in a month. Among those who faced physical attacks over the past year,

42% were attacked by patients, 30.6% by patients' relatives, and 27.4% by hospital staff. The data also indicated that female perpetrators accounted for 62.9% of the attackers, while male perpetrators constituted 37.1%.

Table 2: Frequency of Physical Abuse in the work places

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Frequency of physical attack in the last 12 months(n=388)		
Zero	326	84.0
Once	12	3.1
2-4	21	5.4
5-10	7	1.8
Several times a month	14	3.6
Once a week	8	2.1
The person responsible for the physical abuses (n=62)		
Patient	26	42
Patient relatives	19	30.6
Hospital Staff	17	27.4
Gender of the violator (n=62)		
Male	23	37.1
Female	39	62.9

Table 3 indicates that 61.3% reported no verbal attacks in the last 12 months; 16.5% experienced 2 to 4 attacks; 14.9% were attacked once; and 2.6% were attacked several times a month. In terms of

sources, 42.0% of verbal attacks came from hospital staff, 32.0% from patients, and 26.0% from patients' relatives. Among the perpetrators of verbal attacks, 59.3% were female and 40.7% were male.

Table 3: Frequency of Verbal abuse in the work places in the last 12 months

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Verbal Abuse		
Frequency of verbal attack in the last 12 months (n=388)		
Zero	238	61.3
Once	58	14.9
2-4	64	16.5
5-10	8	2.1
Several times a month	10	2.6
Once a week	8	2.1
Daily	2	0.5
The person responsible for the verbal abuses (n=150)		
Patient	48	32.0
Patient relatives	39	26.0
Hospital Staff	63	42.0
Gender of the violator/Perpetrator (n=150)		
Male	61	40.7
Female	89	59.3

Table 4 illustrates that 303 respondents (78.1%) were not bullied or mobbed at work; 7.2% reported being bullied once, 7.0% experienced bullying 2 to 4 times, and 4.1% were bullied several times a month. The data showed that 43.5% of bullying

incidents were perpetrated by hospital staff, 34.1% by patients' relatives, and 22.4% by patients. Male perpetrators accounted for 54.1% of bullying incidents, while 45.9% were female.

Table 4: Frequency of Bullying/ Mobbing in the work places

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Bullying/Mobbed		
Frequency of attack in the last 12 months (n=388)		
Zero	303	78.1
Once	28	7.2
2-4	27	7.0
5-10	12	3.1
Several times a month	16	4.1
Once a week	2	0.5
The person responsible for the physical abuses (n=85)		
Patient	19	22.4
Patient relatives	29	34.1
Hospital Staff	37	43.5
Gender of the violator/Perpetrator (n=85)		
Male	46	54.1
Female	39	45.9

In table 5, majority of respondents (91.2%) did not experience sexual abuse, while 4.6% experienced it once, 2.1% experienced it 2 to 4 times, and 1.0% experienced it 5 to 10 times. Patients were responsible for 64.7% of sexual abuse incidents,

with both patients' relatives and hospital staff accounting for 17.6% each. Males were responsible for 35.3% of the cases of sexual abuse, while females were responsible for 64.7%.

Table 5: Frequency of Sexual Abuse in the work places

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Sexual Abuse		
Frequency of Sexual Abuse attack in the last 12 months(n=388)		
Zero	354	91.2
Once	18	4.6
2-4	8	2.1
5-10	4	1.0
Several times a month	3	0.8
Once a week	1	0.3
The person responsible for the physical abuses (n=34)		
Patient	22	64.7
Patient relatives	6	17.6
Hospital Staff	6	17.6
Gender of the violator (n=34)		
Male	12	35.3
Female	22	64.7

Table 6 indicates that long waiting times accounted for 50.3% of cases, unprofessional attitudes from healthcare workers accounted for 37.9%, relatives

feeling that patients were in pain and not improving contributed to 34.5%, and lack of security was a factor in 22.7% of cases.

Table 6: Contributing factors to WPV in ESUTH Parklane Enugu

Opinion on the contributing factors	Frequency (n=388)	Percentage (%)
Out-patient not being attended to on time	129	33.2
Relative feel their patients are in pains and not improving	134	34.5
Loss of patients	87	22.4
Feeling that the health workers approach to them	76	19.6
Lack of security	88	22.7
Personality of the perpetrator	80	20.6
Non availability of health workers to attend to them	49	12.6
Shortage of staff	64	16.5
Long waiting time	195	50.3
Healthcare worker's attitude	147	37.9
Lack of bed spaces	87	22.4
Lack of punishment to perpetrators	70	18.0

DISCUSSION:

Workplace violence has been on the increase in our hospitals with significant attendant effects. The majority of healthcare workers in this study are

below 50, and male respondents comprise a significant portion of the study participants, with most being married and identifying as Christians. Notably, nurses represented the highest number of respondents in this study, which mirrors trends seen

in other studies across different regions in Nigeria.^{2,5} This could be because there are usually more nurses employed in healthcare facilities than there are other categories of staff members.

The prevalence of workplace violence revealed that a significant percentage (37.6%) of respondents had experienced all forms of violence assessed in this study (physical attacks, verbal abuse, bullying, and sexual harassment), and this was corroborated by various studies from health facilities across the world including a systematic review on work place violence against primary healthcare workforce worldwide which showed a prevalence of 45.6%-90%.¹⁰ A study on the workplace violence against healthcare workers in Nigeria showed a prevalence ranging from 9-78%.¹¹ Another study in South East Nigeria reported 88.1% prevalence,¹² a study in Northern Nigeria reported 64.45%,² a study in South West Nigeria reported 59.5%,⁵ a study in Palestine reported 80.4%,¹³ and one in China reported 65.8%,¹⁴. This indicates that workplace violence cuts across the country Nigeria and is also a global problem; healthcare workers frequently experience violence in the workplace, with many facing multiple types of violent incidents.

The frequency of various forms of violent attacks was analysed in this study, along with identifying the responsible individuals and their gender. Verbal abuse emerged as the leading form of workplace violence in this study, with a general prevalence rate of 38.7%. This is consistent with findings from other studies as well. A study on the prevalence of psychological workplace violence in Enugu noted a similar high prevalence of verbal abuse (40.8%),³ one in Abia State which is also in South East Region of Nigeria reported 85.4%.¹² Various other studies, both within Nigeria and internationally, have also reported a higher occurrence of verbal abuse compared to other forms of abuse experienced by hospital workers. These include a study in South West Nigeria (85%),¹⁵ a cross-

sectional study conducted by Shi et al. among nurses in China (64.9%),¹⁴ a study done in Palestine (38.3%),¹³ a study in Turkey (71.9%),¹⁶ a study in Egypt (86.1%),¹⁷ a systematic review on violence against primary healthcare workforce worldwide (46.9-90.3%),¹⁰ all of which suggest that verbal abuse is the most common form of abuse experienced by healthcare workers worldwide.

Verbal abuse as indicated by this study was predominantly perpetrated by patients and their relatives (58%), while the remaining 42% came from hospital staff. Furthermore, females were the common perpetrators. This result is similar to reports from other studies on perpetrators of workplace violence. A hospital-based study in the South-western region of Nigeria similarly indicated that workplace based violence was predominantly inflicted by patients or their relatives.⁵ This was also corroborated by later studies in the Eastern part of the country.³ Studies abroad also reported patients or their relatives as the common perpetrators of WPV^{14,17,18,19}

Following verbal abuse, bullying/mobbing was the second most reported incidents (21.9%), physical attacks ranked third in line (16%) and sexual harassment was the least reported (8.8%). While the prevalence of bullying or mobbing in this study was lower than that of verbal abuse, it was still significant at 21.9%, compared to the 7% reported in the other study in Enugu.³ A systematic review on violence against primary healthcare workforce worldwide reported a prevalence of 19-27% for bullying¹⁰. A systematic review on workplace violence amongst nurses in South East Asia and Pacific region reported 17- 33% bullying.²⁰ This goes to show that, as with this study, bullying is another common form of workplace violence.

As with verbal abuse, incidents of bullying were also more frequently linked to patients and their relatives. However, unlike verbal abuse which had a higher incidence of female perpetrators males

were found to be more responsible for bullying in this study. This could be because males often tend to show aggression through intimidation than verbally.

There were 62 cases (16%) of physical abuse recorded in this study. This is relatively lower than the prevalence of 35.4% and 53.3%, respectively, reported by two studies in South Western Nigeria.^{5,15} The lower prevalence in this study might be due to cultural differences in expressing anger and dissatisfaction across the different geopolitical regions of the country. Various other studies across the world also reported incidents of physical abuse. Two studies amongst nurses in China reported 11.8% and 25.77%,^{14,21} a study in Turkey reported 28.1%,¹⁶ a study in Egypt 34.3%,¹⁷ and a study in Palestine 20.8%.¹³ Therefore, physical abuse is another form of workplace violence that healthcare workers face across the globe at one point in their career.

Like the other types of abuse, the perpetration of physical abuse was also found to be more from patients, and by their relatives. In other words, patient-related abuse contributes significantly to incidents of all forms of abuse as has been supported by multiple studies both in Nigeria and abroad.^{3,5,7,11,14,18,17,19} Additionally, like verbal abuse, perpetrators were commonly found to be females. The predominance in female perpetration of abuse in this study might be because, culturally, females are usually the caregivers rather than males, in this part of the world, hence making up the majority of patient relatives.

The prevalence of sexual abuse as a form of workplace violence, although relatively low in this study (8.8%), cannot be overlooked due to its significant impact on the victim's psychology. As with the other forms of abuse, patients and their relatives were often identified as the primary perpetrators of such abuse. Interestingly, in this

study, female perpetrators were reported more than males. This might be due to the disproportionate number of male respondents compared to females. A study also conducted in Enugu reported a low prevalence of sexual abuse³. Nonetheless, the impact of sexual abuse on victims is profound, which means that even low prevalence should not lead to it being ignored. Various other studies reported varying prevalence of sexual abuse, highlighting that it is a very common form of violence faced by healthcare workers. A study in South West Nigeria reported 25.2%,¹⁵ one in Palestine reported 1.7%,¹³ another in China reported 31%,²² one in Egypt reported 48.1%,¹⁶ a study in Nepal reported 5.5%.¹⁸ There is no clear reason to explain this variation in prevalence.

Key contributing factors to workplace violence identified in this study include long waiting times (50.3%), healthcare workers' attitudes (37.9%), and relatives feeling that patients were in pain and not improving (34.5%), and delays in attending to outpatients (33.2%).

Other studies in Nigeria on WPV have also reported similar contributing factors. A study in Northern Nigeria reported long waiting times in 67.3% of incidents of WPV.² Another study in South West Nigeria similarly reported waiting time to contribute 80.6%, healthcare workers' attitude 61.8%, and patients in pain and not improving 28.5%.⁵ These similar findings could be due to a shortage of staff to attend to the patients quickly enough, which is common across the country, and also due to similar cultural and behavioural patterns amongst the people in the country.

Other contributing factors in this study were loss of patients, perceptions that the healthcare workers' approach was inappropriate, lack of security, unavailability of healthcare staff, shortage of personnel, lack of bed space, and insufficient punishment for perpetrators. It is important to note that many of these issues are patient-centred and

directly affect the patients, which is why most of the violence was perpetrated by patients and their relatives.

CONCLUSION:

The prevalence of workplace violence in this study is high, several forms of workplace violence were assessed, with verbal abuse being the most common form. Patients and their relatives were identified as the primary perpetrators of workplace violence, influenced largely by patient-related factors; therefore, measures should be put in place to tackle these factors so as to reduce the incidence of workplace violence.

Conflict of Interest:

None

Sponsorship

None

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